

Temperature dependence of Young's modulus, damping and dilatation during repeated thermal cycling of silica refractories for high-temperature thermal energy storage (TES)

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ABSTRACT

Silica refractories are traditional materials for several important niche applications (e.g. coke oven linings and glass melter roofs) but are also potential candidates for modern high-temperature thermal energy storage. For this application all aspects of its high-temperature behavior must be thoroughly known. In this paper the temperature dependence of Young's modulus and damping of silica refractories is investigated via impulse excitation during (three times repeated) heating to 900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C and cooling back to room temperature. Apart from the well-known hysteresis effects, induced by changes in the phase composition (based on tridymite and cristobalite) and microstructure (crack closure and re-opening), it is shown that cycling to 900 and 1100 °C leads to damage accumulation, while heating to 1300 and 1500 °C does not, and in the latter case a new type of elastic anomaly is observed during reheating. Damping and hysteresis parameters are discussed as well.

1. Introduction

Silica refractories have been invented by William Weston Young (1776–1847) more than two centuries years ago (1820–1821) and patented by him in 1822 [1–3]. Their historical importance consisted in the fact that they represented a significant improvement over conventional fireclay refractories, because they were the first material usable to temperatures above 1600 °C without softening, which is a consequence of the generally low glass phase content and the high creep resistance. Although the demand of silica refractories is relatively low today, because its use in the iron and steel industry has decreased in the last decades and because the lifetime of silica refractories is very long, there are important niche applications in which silica refractories are irreplaceable, such as coke oven linings, glass melter roofs, special furnaces for non-iron metallurgy and the ceramic industry, and blast furnace recuperators (Cowpers) [4–12]. The renewed research interest in silica refractories during the last few years [13–19] has mainly been triggered

by these traditional applications in which the high creep resistance of silica refractories plays a decisive role [20].

A new field of application for which silica refractories can be potentially useful candidates is high-temperature thermal energy storage (TES) for solar energy. In particular, at temperatures above 600 °C silica refractories can be expected to have a very long lifetime under thermal cycling conditions, because thermal expansion is very low in this temperature range. With respect to the traditional applications of silica refractories, where the heating rates are extremely slow (during the heat-up stage after the installation of a high-temperature aggregate) and where the operation temperatures remain constantly above 600 °C (falling below this temperature only when repairing or demounting the high-temperature aggregate), thermal cycling of silica refractories to temperatures below 600 °C has not been a major topic of research in the literature so far, with a few exceptions, in which selected aspects of this cycling behavior have been treated [21–26]. However, in contrast to the traditional applications of silica refractories, for modern TES

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applications the thermal cycling behavior down to room temperature can become an important topic. Therefore, in the present work, we investigate systematically and in detail the effects of thermal cycling from room temperature to high temperatures (900–1500 °C) and back down to room temperature on Young's modulus, damping and dilatation, in order to assess whether and to what degree silica refractories can survive such cycling conditions.

In previous work it has been shown that the impulse excitation technique (IET) is an ideal method to monitor the temperature dependence of Young's modulus and damping of silica refractories [21–24]. In particular, it has been shown that the temperature dependence of Young's modulus shows reproducible hysteresis with characteristic anomalies related to the phase transitions of cristobalite and tridymite [21–23]. Further, it has been shown that the hysteresis, which is related to microcrack closure during heating and microcrack re-opening during cooling, describes a closed loop (without any indication of damage accumulation) when the maximum temperature during thermal cycling is 1200 °C [21,23], whereas the loop opens up (thus indicating damage accumulation) when the maximum temperature during thermal cycling is 800 or 1000 °C [22]. These results have recently been nicely confirmed in the careful work by Yin et al. [26]. For maximum temperatures of 1200 °C it has also been shown that the anomalies in the temperature dependence of Young's modulus occur at the same temperatures as the changes in the slope of dilatation curves, thus reflecting the phase transitions of cristobalite and tridymite during heating [23]. Also these findings have later been studied in a very systematic way in the work by Yin et al. [26]. Last but not least, the temperature of damping has been recorded in a single cycle during heating and cooling with a maximum temperature of 1200 °C [24], and it has been shown that damping can provide additional information and possibly hint towards the presence of calcium silicate phases that are present in amounts too low to be detectable by X-ray diffraction. Most of the early IET measurements have been made for a maximum temperature of 1200 °C, where the hysteresis loop is closed and damage accumulation does not occur [21–24]. Only our previous paper [22] and the paper by Yin et al. [26] have studied the cycling behavior also for cycle maximum temperatures (CMTs) of 800 and 1000 °C, but without analyzing the temperature dependence of anelastic effects (damping). Higher CMTs than 1200 °C have been investigated by the IET only exceptionally. In particular, Andreev et al. [25] measured Young's modulus up to 1300 °C and, albeit not fully convincing in the high-temperature region and only based on one heating-cooling cycle, the findings of their work confirm that cycling to 1300 °C does not lead to damage and seem to indicate that it might even lead to healing. Unfortunately, also in that work, the temperature dependence of damping is not analyzed. From this brief summary of the state of the art it follows that IET measurements with repeated thermal cycling to temperatures higher than 1200 °C have not been performed and that IET data describing the degree of damage or healing during repeated cycling are not available so far. Also no attempt has been made to quantify the hysteresis behavior. With the exception of our previous paper [24], where results are shown for two cycles to 1200 °C only, the temperature of damping during thermal cycling has not been studied at all. The present paper intends to fill these gaps by systematic IET measurements (temperature dependence of Young's modulus and damping) of silica refractories for three repeated thermal cycles (heating and cooling) with maximum temperatures of 900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C. The results of IET measurements are correlated with the results of dilatometric measurements, and damage and hysteresis parameters are shown as functions of the cycle number and temperature, respectively.

2. Experimental methods and evaluation procedures

The silica refractory material investigated in this work (a prototype material supplied by P-D Refractories CZ a.s., Czech Republic, now RHI Magnesita Czech Republic a.s.) was prepared from milled quartzite with

a grain size of up to ~3 mm as the main component, with minor additions of quartz sand with a grain size below 1 mm and silica powder with a grain size below 90 µm. After homogenization in the dry state, CaO has been added in the form of dry hydrated lime Ca(OH)₂, resulting in a CaO content of ~4 %. Water has been added to achieve a humidity of ~5 % in the mixture. After pressing at ~50 MPa the materials have been dried and subsequently fired at 1430 °C according to a proprietary schedule. The chemical composition of this silica refractory has been measured by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis on a PERFORM X spectrometer (Thermo ARL, Switzerland) and calculated by UniQuant software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The phase composition has been determined on powders prepared by crushing and milling silica refractories in the as-supplied state (i.e. uncycled) as well as after three complete thermal cycles (heating from and cooling to room temperature) with a cycle maximum temperature (CMT) of 1500 °C by X-ray diffraction (XRD) in an Empyrean Series 3 diffractometer (Malvern PANalytical, The Netherlands), equipped with a conventional X-ray tube (CoK α radiation, 40 kV, 30 mA, line focus), multicore optics and a linear position sensitive PIXCel3D detector, using conventional Bragg-Brentano geometry. X-ray patterns were collected in the 2 θ range 10° to 90° with a step size of 0.0131° and 200 s per step. Quantitative phase analysis was performed via Rietveld refinement [27], using the High-ScorePlus software package version 5.2.0 (Malvern PANalytical, The Netherlands) [28] and the PDF-5+ database [29]. The amorphous phase content has been determined via the internal standard method [30], using ZnO as an internal standard. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in the backscattered electron (BSE) mode and energy-dispersive spectrometry (EDS) have been performed on polished sections on a Lyra3 instrument (Tescan, Czech Republic). Bulk density and open porosity have been determined via the Archimedes method, using water as a soaking liquid. Pore size distributions, together with apparent density, bulk density and open porosity have been determined via mercury porosimetry on an Autopore IV 9500 V1.10 porosimeter (Micromeritics, USA), with cumulative size distributions being subsequently normalized to 100 %. Dilatometric measurements have been performed for an uncycled sample and for samples after three thermal cycles with CMTs of 900 and 1500 °C on a DIL 402 C (Netzsch, Germany) during heating from room temperature to 1450 °C, cooling to 160 °C and a second heating-cooling cycle starting and ending at 160 °C with the same CMT (1450 °C), using heating and cooling rates of 5 °C/min. The temperature of 1450 °C corresponds approximately to the maximum firing temperature at which the investigated silica refractories had been originally produced (1430 °C). Both apparent and true expansion coefficients have been determined numerically from the dilatometric curves (relative length change versus temperature). Irreversible length changes have been determined by measuring the initial sample dimensions and the actual sample dimensions after cycling using a digital slide caliper.

The impulse excitation technique (IET) measurements have been performed according to the relevant ASTM standards [31,32], using flexural vibrations of bar-shaped specimens with dimensions 104 × 27 × 8 (±1) mm. In particular, Young's modulus was determined from the resonant frequency of these flexural vibrations via the formula

$$E = 0.9465 \cdot (mf^2) \cdot \left(\frac{L^3}{bh^3}\right) \cdot \Psi \left(\nu, \frac{h}{L}\right) \quad (1)$$

where f is the resonant frequency (fundamental mode), m the sample mass, L its length, b its width, h its height, and Ψ is a sample shape correction factor that depends on the Poisson ratio ν and the aspect ratio of the sample (and is for our samples very close to unity). Damping, as defined via the so-called inverse quality factor

$$Q^{-1} = \frac{k}{\pi f} \quad (2)$$

was determined from the amplitude decay constant k of an exponential fit to the decreasing amplitude hull curve of the flexural vibration. This

is a valid approximation if $Q^{-1} < 0.1$ [33]. The instrumental equipment used for these IET measurements was a Resonant Frequency and Damping Analyzer (RDFA 23, IMCE, Belgium) integrated in a high-temperature furnace (HT 1600, IMCE, Belgium). For thermal cycling, the heating and cooling rates have been set to 5 °C/min and cycle maximum temperatures (CMTs) have been chosen to be 900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C. For each of these CMTs, IET measurements have been performed during three complete heating-cooling cycles. Fig. 1 shows a silica refractory sample after thermal cycling to 1500 °C (three times), as positioned on the sample support in the high-temperature furnace.

Based on the Young's modulus values before and after cycling, (cumulative) damage parameters defined as

$$D_E = 1 - \frac{E_{final}(20^\circ\text{C})}{E_{initial}(20^\circ\text{C})} \quad (3)$$

have been calculated, where $E_{initial}(20^\circ\text{C})$ and $E_{final}(20^\circ\text{C})$ are the initial and final values of Young's modulus at room temperature, respectively (i.e. the room temperature values of Young's modulus before and after cycling). On the other hand, during each individual cycle incremental hysteresis parameters

$$\omega_E = 1 - \frac{E_{down}^{i-th}(T)}{E_{up}^{i-th}(T)} \quad (4)$$

have been calculated as functions of temperature, where $E_{down}^{i-th}(T)$ and $E_{up}^{i-th}(T)$ are the Young's modulus values of the i -th cycle at temperature T during heating and cooling, respectively. Similarly, for repeated cycling, cumulative hysteresis parameters

$$\Omega_E = 1 - \frac{E_{down}^{i-th}(T)}{E_{up}^{first}(T)} \quad (5)$$

have been calculated as functions of temperature, where $E_{up}^{first}(T)$ is the Young's modulus of the first cycle at temperature T during heating. In contrast to the (cumulative) damage parameter, characterizing irreversible changes due to thermal cycling, the hysteresis parameters characterize the potential to tailor the elastic properties of silica refractories just by controlling the thermal history. Negative values of the hysteresis parameters indicate that for a given temperature Young's modulus is higher during cooling than during heating.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 lists the chemical composition of the silica refractory

Fig. 1. Silica refractory sample after thermal cycling (three times) to 1500 °C, as positioned on the sample support in the high-temperature furnace.

Table 1

Chemical composition of the investigated silica refractory samples, as determined via X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis.

Oxide	SiO ₂	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O
Content	94.2	4.3	0.62 ±	0.45 ±	0.12	0.04 ±	0.16
[wt%]	± 0.3	± 0.2	0.04	0.02	± 0.01	0.01	± 0.01

investigated in this work, as determined via X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis. Compared to the silica refractory types investigated in our previous paper [22], where the content of calcium oxide was 1.2–2.5 wt %, the specific type investigated in the present work has a relatively high CaO content of 4.3 wt%, at the cost of SiO₂ (here only 94.2 wt%, compared to 95.2–96.7 wt% for similar products). The content of the other oxides, including Fe₂O₃ and Al₂O₃, is typical for high-quality silica refractories.

Table 2 lists the phase contents (in wt%) of the silica refractory in the pristine state (as-supplied, uncycled) and after threefold thermal cycling with a cycle maximum temperature (CMT) of 1500 °C during the impulse excitation technique (IET) measurement, determined via X-ray diffraction (XRD). It is evident that the as-supplied (uncycled) material contains a small amount (approximately 2 %) of glass phase (amorphous phase), whereas after cycling to the highest temperature (CMT 1500 °C) the glass phase content has increased to approximately 10 %. At the same time, after threefold cycling to 1500 °C, the pseudowollastonite contained in the pristine material (approximately 6 %) has disappeared, i.e. has completely dissolved in the glass phase. This can be clearly seen in the SEM micrographs (obtained by backscattered electron imaging) shown in Fig. 2. The micrographs in the upper row (A, B) show the uncycled material, the micrographs in the bottom row (C, D) show the material after threefold thermal cycling to 1500 °C. The former show well-rounded isometric pseudowollastonite crystallites (with a size around 5 μm), together with dendrites of another crystalline phase that could not be identified by XRD in the glass phase between the idiomorphic anisometric tridymite crystals. Although unidentified by XRD, the bright color in the backscattered electron imaging strongly suggests the presence of Fe in these dendrites, which could be confirmed via local EDS probing, so that possible candidates for the dendrites visible in the uncycled material are iron monticellite CFS, dicalcium ferrite C₂F or brownmillerite C₄AF. After threefold thermal cycling to 1500 °C both the pseudowollastonite crystals and the dendrites have completely disappeared and have obviously dissolved in the glass melt, so that the interparticle space between the tridymite crystals is filled by a homogeneous glass phase.

Typical glass phase contents reported for silica refractories in the literature are in the range 6–8 wt% [10,11], but the opinions concerning this question differ from completely absent [20] or only cryptocrystalline (albeit apparently X-ray amorphous) to approximately 20 wt%, see also the discussion in our previous paper [22]. It is plausible that these discrepancies concerning the glass phase content are not only a consequence of the different chemical composition (e.g. the CaO content) but also a consequence of the thermal history, as shown in Fig. 2. It should be noted that the CMT of 1500 °C is higher than the original firing temperature of around 1430 °C used for the production of these silica refractories, so that the originally crystalline calcium silicate phase (pseudowollastonite) present in the as-supplied material has evidently been fully dissolved in the glass melt. On the other hand, the cooling rate used in the IET measurements (nominally 5 °C/min) is much higher than that used in the production of silica refractories (order of magnitude 0.1–0.5 °C/min), so that during cooling in the IET furnace the glass phase does not have enough time to recrystallize. Last but not least, it should be noted that the tridymite-cristobalite ratio decreases slightly from 1.06 for the as-supplied material to 0.94 for the material after threefold cycling to 1500 °C, see Table 2, as expected on the base of phase equilibrium considerations when the temperature is higher than 1470 °C (the equilibrium transition temperature from tridymite to

Table 2

Crystalline phase contents (in wt%) of the silica refractory in the as-supplied state (uncycled) and after threefold cycling with a CMT of 1500 °C during the IET measurement, determined via X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) with ZnO as an internal standard, including the ratio of tridymite and cristobalite (T/C ratio).

CMT	Cristobalite	Tridymite	Pseudowollastonite	Amorphous	T/C ratio
As-supplied	44.7	47.5	6.0	1.8	1.06
1500 °C	46.5	43.6	-	9.9	0.94

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs (obtained by backscattered electron imaging) of polished sections of the silica refractories studied in this paper: unycled (A, B), after threefold thermal cycling to 1500 °C (C, D); note that the unycled material contains pseudowollastonite grains and dendrites between the tridymite crystals, while the material after cycling contains a homogeneous glass phase completely filling the intergranular space between the tridymite crystals.

cristobalite). Quartz has not been detected in the investigated materials by XRD and also the IET measurements (see below) do not show any indication of residual quartz. Parts A and C of Fig. 2 also show the character of the pore space, which is essentially open and interconnected.

Fig. 3 shows silica refractory samples after thermal cycling (three times) to 900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C. The samples with CMTs in the range 900–1300 °C do not show any visible alterations and are indistinguishable from the pristine (as-supplied, unycled) material, whereas the sample cycled with a CMT of 1500 °C reveals alterations that are immediately visible by visual inspection as an overall decoloration (brightening), while residual regions with the original color appear as isolated dark patches on the surface, probably suggesting that during heating to 1500 °C the ferric ions have changed their coordination number as a consequence of their dissolution in the glass phase.

Table 3 lists the basic microstructural characteristics determined via

the Archimedes method (AM) and mercury porosimetry (MP) for silica samples in the as-supplied state (uncycled) and after threefold cycling to different CMTs during the IET measurement. It is evident that the bulk density and (open) porosity of $1.833 \pm 0.004 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $21.0 \pm 0.2 \%$ determined via the Archimedes method is in excellent agreement with the corresponding values determined via mercury porosimetry. Both values are typical for silica refractories, when compared to the data reported in the literature [10–12,21–24]. Also the apparent density determined via mercury porosimetry is very close to typical data reported for silica refractories in the literature [10–12] and close to the theoretical densities of cristobalite (2.32 g/cm^3) and tridymite (2.26 g/cm^3) [34], which indicates a perfect conversion from quartz to cristobalite and tridymite and is in agreement with the XRD findings, i.e. the absence of any detectable amount of residual quartz, see Table 2. A detailed view on the data in Table 3 for the individual samples after thermal cycling does not reveal any significant changes of bulk density

Fig. 3. Silica refractory samples after thermal cycling (three times) to 900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C (from left to right); note that only the sample cycled with a CMT of 1500 °C reveals alterations that are immediately visible by visual inspection.

or porosity due to thermal cycling.

However, the pore size distributions in Figs. 4 and 5 show small but reproducible differences between the uncycled sample and the samples cycled with CMTs of 900 and 1100 °C on the one hand, and the samples cycled with CMTs of 1300 and 1500 °C on the other hand. These pore size distributions, more precisely the volume-weighted distributions of equivalent pore throat diameters, are trimodal in all cases, with a sub-10-nm mode belonging to nanoscopic features that are irrelevant in the present context (probably the nanocracks within the cristobalite grains which are responsible for the well-known “roof-tile” structure within individual cristobalite grains [35]), a submicrometer mode that has to be attributed to microcracks and a supermicrometer mode that represents mainly the throats to the pores that are responsible for the overall porosity of 21 %.

In particular, Fig. 4 shows that the submicrometer pore size mode is smaller (414–417 nm) for CMTs 1300 and 1500 °C than for CMTs 900 and 1100 °C (501–504 nm), although both are larger than in the pristine (uncycled) material (335 nm). This strongly suggests that this mode represents microcracks. It is thus clear that all types of thermal cycling increase the submicrometer mode (attributable to microcracks) but thermal cycling with lower CMTs (900 and 1100 °C) leaves larger submicrometer pores (microcracks) than cycling with higher CMTs (1300 and 1500 °C). This indicates healing (microcrack closure) mediated by the glass melt.

On the other hand, the supermicrometer pore size mode is larger (16.7 μm) for CMTs 1300 and 1500 °C than for CMTs 900 and 1100 °C (12.5 μm). The same relation is reflected in the overall median pore size (18.7–18.8 μm versus 16.2–17.0 μm), see Table 3 and Fig. 5. For comparison, the uncycled sample has a supermicrometer mode of 12.5 μm and a median pore size of 16.8 μm. This finding is at first sight remarkable but can be explained by the fact that part of the smaller pore throats have been closed by the glass melt.

Both effects, the aforementioned healing (shift of the submicrometer mode to smaller sizes via the closure of microcracks) and the apparent pore growth (shift of the supermicrometer mode to larger sizes via the closure of small pore throats) can be explained by the action of the glass melt at high temperature, especially when its amount increases and its composition, structure and properties undergo changes.

Dimensional measurements via a slide caliper reveal that the silica samples undergo very slight irreversible dimensional changes due to cycling, with a linear irreversible expansion of around 0.4 ± 0.2 % after cooling, but without a clear correlation to the cycle number or the CMT, see Table 4. This finding is in agreement with the fact that the residual

Table 3 Basic microstructural characteristics determined via the Archimedes method (AM) and mercury porosimetry (MP) for silica samples in the as-supplied state (uncycled) and after threefold cycling with different CMTs during the IET measurement.

CMT	Bulk density (AM) [g/cm ³]	Bulk density (MP) [g/cm ³]	Apparent density (MP) [g/cm ³]	Open porosity (AM) [%]	Open porosity (MP) [%]	Median pore diameter (MP) [μm]	Super-micro-meter pore size mode (MP) [μm]	Submicro-meter pore size mode (MP) [nm]
As-supplied	1.833 ± 0.004	1.831	2.327	21.0 ± 0.2	21.3	16.8	12.5	335
900 °C	1.836	1.850	2.332	20.8	20.7	16.2	12.5	504
1100 °C	1.836	1.840	2.315	20.7	20.5	17.0	12.5	501
1300 °C	1.828	1.825	2.316	21.1	21.2	18.7	16.7	417
1500 °C	1.837	1.813	2.313	20.7	21.6	18.8	16.7	414

Fig. 4. Pore size distribution (volume-weighted frequency distribution of equivalent cylinder pore throat diameters) of silica refractory samples in the as-supplied state (uncycled) and after three thermal cycles with CMTs of 900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C.

Fig. 5. Pore size distribution (volume-weighted cumulative distribution of equivalent cylinder pore throat diameters) of silica refractory samples in the as-supplied state (uncycled) and after three thermal cycles with CMTs of 900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C.

Table 4

Irreversible dimensional changes after thermal cycling (linear expansion in %, cumulative values related to the initial dimensions before cycling, measured with a slide caliper).

CMT	First cycle	Second cycle	Third cycle
900 °C	0.43 ± 0.36	0.39 ± 0.28	0.35 ± 0.03
1100 °C	0.28 ± 0.18	0.53 ± 0.31	0.56 ± 0.16
1300 °C	0.12 ± 0.15	0.18 ± 0.12	0.27 ± 0.07
1500 °C	0.45 ± 0.34	0.38 ± 0.22	0.70 ± 0.38
Average	0.32 ± 0.26	0.37 ± 0.23	0.47 ± 0.20

quartz content is negligibly low and indicates that also other changes of phase composition and microstructure (microcracking) have only a negligible influence on the irreversible dimensional changes. From the viewpoint of practice, such an irreversible expansion of 0.4 % will be negligible for most applications, including TES.

Dilatometric measurements show that the maximum values of reversible relative length changes during the first heating are 1.30, 1.32 and 1.26 % for uncycled samples and samples three times cycled with CMTs of 900 and 1500 °C, respectively, see Figs. 6 through 8. In the temperature range between 800 and 1300 °C the dimensions of the samples remain almost constant, while above 1300 °C a slight shrinkage

Fig. 6. Dilatometric curves for two heating-cooling cycles (first from room temperature to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C, second from 160 °C to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C) for as-supplied (i.e. previously uncycled) silica refractory samples.

Fig. 7. Dilatometric curves for two heating-cooling cycles (first from room temperature to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C, second from 160 °C to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C) for silica refractory samples three times cycled with a CMT of 900 °C.

Fig. 8. Dilatometric curves for two heating-cooling cycles (first from room temperature to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C, second from 160 °C to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C) for silica refractory samples three times cycled with a CMT of 1500 °C.

(< 0.2 %) is observed that may be caused by the formation of a glass melt (not only by softening of the small initial glass phase content, but also by the increased glass melt volume caused by the dissolution of

pseudowollastonite crystals and dendrites).

Characteristic temperatures of the dilatometric curves, determined from the maxima of the true expansion coefficients, see Appendix A, are listed in Table 5. It is evident that these temperatures correspond to the two phase transitions of tridymite at 112–115 °C and 143–150 °C, respectively (here determined only during the first heating, because the first cooling as well as the whole second cycle end and start at 160 °C) and to the transition of cristobalite with its well-known hysteresis, i.e. 231–241 °C during heating and 199 ± 1 °C during cooling. There is no indication that thermal cycling would affect these transition temperatures in any way.

In order to compare the dilatation behavior of silica refractories, the length changes of uncycled and cycled (three times cycled with CMTs of 900 and 1500 °C) materials were recorded in two cycles, first from room temperature to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C and then from 160 °C to 1450 °C and back, see Figs. 6 through 8. The cooling branches of the dilatation curves are almost identical for the first and second cycle, while the heating branches are of course different because of the different reference length in the two cycles (for the first it is the initial length at room temperature, for the second the actual length at 160 °C). Therefore, the temperature dependences of the true expansion coefficients in Appendix A are almost identical for both cycles (while for the apparent expansion coefficients they exhibit systematic differences between the first and second heating). Therefore a fair comparison of the dilatation curves during heating is only possible when the curves referring to the second heating are rescaled with respect to the actual length of the sample at 160 °C, see Fig. 9. This comparison shows that thermal cycling to 1450 °C (during the dilatometric measurement) leads to a very slight decrease of thermal expansion, but – as expected – only in those samples that have not undergone previous thermal cycling to 1500 °C (during the IET measurement). From the viewpoint of practical applications, however, these differences are almost negligible (< 0.1 %). From all these results, taking experimental data scatter and sample-to-sample variations into account, it may be concluded that thermal cycling does not affect the thermal expansion behavior significantly, even when the CMT is 1500 °C and initially crystalline phases are incorporated into the glass melt at high temperature and remain dissolved in the glass phase during cooling.

Figs. 10 through 13 show the temperature dependence of Young's modulus for three complete heating-cooling cycles with CMTs of 900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C. The cooling branches of all cycles have been corrected with respect to the (very small) dimensional changes due to the preceding heating. It is evident that in all cases there is a complex hysteresis behavior between heating and cooling. This hysteresis behavior, which is typical for silica refractories and has been discussed in detail in previous papers [21–24], concerns both the difference in Young's modulus values (vertical direction, i.e. ordinate values) and the difference in the phase transition temperatures between the low- and high-temperature forms of cristobalite and tridymite (horizontal direction, i.e. abscissa values).

For the explanation of this complex hysteresis behavior it has to be recalled that during heating and cooling the phase transitions themselves are known to occur at different temperatures, which explains the reproducible shift of the transition temperature between heating and

Table 5

Characteristic temperatures (in °C) of the dilatation curves (maxima of the true expansion coefficients), as determined via dilatometric measurements, see Appendix A.

CMT	First heating	First cooling	Second heating	Second cooling
As-supplied	112, 150, 234	201	235	202
900 °C	112, 147, 232	200	236	199
1500 °C	114, 143, 231–241	198	240	199

Fig. 9. Comparison of dilatometric curves for two heating branches (first from room temperature to 1450 °C, second from 160 °C to 1450 °C, but rescaled to the actual sample length at 160 °C) for cycled and uncycled silica refractory samples.

Fig. 10. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for three complete heating-cooling cycles with a CMT of 900 °C.

Fig. 11. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for three complete heating-cooling cycles with a CMT of 1100 °C.

cooling. This is a phenomenon on the atomistic scale and can be related to the kinetics of the displacive phase transition (which occurs at higher temperature during heating, at lower temperature during cooling). On the other hand, the discrepancy between the heating and cooling branches is a microstructural phenomenon, caused by microcrack closure during heating and delayed microcrack re-opening during

Fig. 12. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for three complete heating-cooling cycles with a CMT of 1300 °C.

Fig. 13. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for three complete heating-cooling cycles with a CMT of 1500 °C.

cooling [36]. Similar phenomena, of course without the additional complication of phase transitions, are known for cordierite ceramics [37–39] and β -eucryptite ceramics [40,41].

Apart from these ubiquitous general features of Figs. 10 through 13, however, the individual heating-cooling cycles exhibit significant and very characteristic differences. When the CMT is 900 °C or 1100 °C, the curves (both heating and cooling branches) of the first cycle are on a significantly higher level than those of the following cycles (i.e. second and third cycle), which indicates severe damage accumulation (so that Young's modulus after cooling is significantly lower than before heating), whereas for CMTs of 1300 and 1500 °C just the opposite is observed: the first heating curves are always significantly lower than the second and third ones, and damage accumulation after the heating-cooling cycles is even replaced by a slight increase of Young's modulus, which indicates healing (mainly via the closure of microcracks). Fig. 14 shows the (cumulative) damage parameters according to Eq. 3 as a function of the cycle number. It is evident that for a CMT of 900 °C the degree of damage accumulation is much higher than for a CMT of 1100 °C, while for CMTs of 1300 and 1500 °C there is even a certain degree of healing. This result corresponds very well to previous findings on similar silica refractories which indicate that the Young's modulus hysteresis loop is completely closed and reproducible for a CMT of 1200 °C (i.e. neither damage accumulation nor crack healing are observed) [21,23], whereas for CMTs of 800 and 1000 °C damage accumulation has been observed [22].

Going into further detail, one may observe that between 1000 and 1100 °C the heating branches of the curves with CMTs of 1100, 1300 and

Fig. 14. Damage parameters (based on the values of Young's modulus before heating and after cooling) as a function the number of cycles (cycle number); the connecting lines are only a guide to the eye.

1500 °C all exhibit a maximum in Young's modulus (the heating curve to 900 °C ends before this maximum is achieved). When the CMT is 1100 °C, this Young's modulus maximum is highest for the first cycle and decreases with increasing cycle number, whereas for CMTs of 1300 and 1500 °C it is lowest for the first cycle and increases with increasing cycle number. Most remarkable, however, is the fact that for a CMT of 1500 °C, more precisely after the first complete heating-cooling cycle to 1500 °C, Young's modulus decreases steeply above 800 °C and a sharp local minimum appears at around 1000 °C in the heating curves of the subsequent cycles, followed by a steep increase to a maximum at around 1060 °C and a shoulder at around 1170 °C. This behavior is completely reproducible, and there is no doubt that it would occur in subsequent thermal cycles as well. Since this anomaly in the temperature dependence of Young's modulus does not occur for lower CMTs, it must be related to the fact that the CMT of 1500 °C, which is higher than the original firing temperature of the silica refractory (1430 °C) and the eutectic temperature between SiO_2 / tridymite and CaSiO_3 / pseudowollastonite (1436 °C), results in the dissolution of pseudowollastonite crystals (and the dendrites) in the glass melt and the ensuing increase in the glass phase content after the first heating-cooling cycle with CMT 1500 °C, see Fig. 2. The dissolution of pseudowollastonite and dendrites leads to compositional and structural changes in the glass melt (mainly due to the enrichment with CaO), entailing changes in the glass properties (e.g. its viscosity and surface tension) and its softening behavior. Moreover, the content of glass melt is of course increased at the cost of the dissolved crystalline phases (pseudowollastonite, dendrites) which completely disappear during the first heating to 1500 °C and have no time to recrystallize during cooling. Therefore, the heating branches of the subsequent cycles are affected by the softening of this (CaO-rich) glass phase at a relatively low temperature (slightly above 800 °C), which explains the decrease of Young's modulus above this temperature. It is plausible that the CaO-rich glass has a lower softening range than the original glass, which can be assumed to be almost CaO-free. However, the reason for the subsequent steep increase in Young's modulus is not clear and requires further investigation in future work. A possible explanation would be the (thermally activated) transient crystallization of cristobalite and tridymite from the glass melt and their subsequent re-dissolution in the glass melt at higher temperatures. Interestingly, at temperatures above 1300 °C the elastic behavior of cycled materials is indistinguishable from that of uncycled ones, see Fig. 13. This is obviously the consequence of the existence of a homogeneous glass melt, without pseudowollastonite crystals and dendrites, above this temperature. It is highly probable that not only the increased amount of glass melt available but also the property changes induced in the glass melt by changes of its composition above 1300 °C enable the healing of microcracks.

In this context it may also be recalled that a temperature of 1470 °C is usually considered to be the transition temperature at which tridymite transforms into cristobalite (under equilibrium conditions). Indeed, the XRD results listed in Table 2 indicate a slight increase of the cristobalite content at the cost of tridymite, when cycling has been performed with a CMT of 1500 °C. It is questionable, however, whether such a small change in the tridymite-to-cristobalite (T/C) ratio can have any sensible effect on the elastic properties of silica refractories and their temperature dependence.

Interestingly, the cooling curves from the CMT of 1500 °C do not show any elastic anomaly of the type described above for the heating curves, see Fig. 13, but due to the CaO-enrichment of the glass melt and the absence of a “particulate” skeleton of pseudowollastonite crystals and the dendrites the material cycled to 1500 °C stiffens during cooling at a significantly lower temperature (< 1000 °C) than the materials cycled with lower CMTs.

Figs. 15, 16 and 17 compare, for the first, second and third cycles, respectively, the heating branches for Young’s modulus values normalized to their room temperature values before heating. When starting from room temperature it is seen that in all cases Young’s modulus decreases and achieves a minimum at 210–220 °C that is less than 65 % of its room temperature value. Fig. 15, which refers to the first heating, shows that during further heating Young’s modulus increases and achieves a maximum at around 1100 °C that is about 200 % of its room temperature value. At even higher temperatures Young’s modulus decreases again and tends towards a value that is at 1500 °C still more than 150 % of its room temperature value, which is quite remarkable (because at this temperature the material should contain approximately 10 % of glass melt). It has to be noted that in principle all four heating curves should be identical up to 900 °C. That means, the difference between the curves up to this temperature only represents the statistical sample-to-sample variability, caused by the heterogeneous coarse-grained microstructure of the materials. Figs. 16 and 17, referring to the second and third heating, respectively, show similar overall behavior, but systematic and characteristic differences in detail. In particular, for CMTs of 1300 °C and below the maximum of Young’s modulus is shifted to slightly lower temperatures (below 1050 °C) and for CMT 1500 °C Young’s modulus exhibits the aforementioned sharp maximum at around 1060 °C with a shoulder at around 1170 °C which is preceded by a decrease of Young’s modulus in the temperature range 850–1000 °C. As mentioned above, this unusual behavior must be attributed to the fact that heating to 1500 °C (i.e. to a higher temperature than the original firing temperature of 1450 °C) causes the formation of a glass melt that appears as a (CaO-rich) glass phase after cooling.

Fig. 18 shows the temperature dependence of the incremental hysteresis parameter ω_E according to Eq. 4. It has to be recalled that this parameter is negative when Young’s modulus is higher during cooling

Fig. 15. Normalized Young’s modulus (with respect to the room temperature value before heating) as a function of temperature; first heating.

Fig. 16. Normalized Young’s modulus (with respect to the room temperature value before heating) as a function of temperature; second heating.

Fig. 17. Normalized Young’s modulus (with respect to the room temperature value before heating) as a function of temperature; third heating.

Fig. 18. Incremental hysteresis parameter as a function of temperature.

than during heating and *vice versa*. An overall comparison shows that at 100 °C ω_E is positive in all cases, indicating that at this temperature Young’s modulus is always lower during cooling than during heating (by 16–47 %). On the other hand, in the temperature range 300–900 °C ω_E is negative in all cases, indicating that in this temperature range Young’s modulus is always higher during cooling than during heating, with most extreme values around 500 °C. Samples subjected to heating-cooling cycles with CMTs 1300 and 1500 °C exhibit negative ω_E values in an

even broader temperature range (200–1000 °C) and attain most extreme values (–110 % and –123 %, respectively) at 500 °C. In other words, a silica refractory to be used at 500 °C is stiffer by 110 or 123 % if subjected to preheating to 1300 or 1500 °C, respectively, and then cooled down to 500 °C before use, compared to a silica refractory that is directly heated up to 500 °C from room temperature. Or, put differently, a silica refractory that has attained an operation temperature of 500 °C by cooling down from 1300–1500 °C is much less compliant than the same silica refractory that has attained the same temperature by heating up from room temperature.

Fig. 19 shows the temperature dependence of the cumulative hysteresis parameter Ω_E according to Eq. 5. This parameter quantifies the overall changes in Young's modulus that can be achieved by cooling to a certain temperature after repeated heating-cooling cycles. In the special case of room temperature this hysteresis parameter equals the aforementioned damage parameter D_E , see Eq. 3 and Fig. 14. In contrast to Fig. 18, which quantifies these changes within each individual heating-cooling cycle, Fig. 19 quantifies the changes due to repeated cycling. It is evident that negative values of the cumulative hysteresis parameter Ω_E , i.e. higher Young's modulus during cooling than during heating, are observed between 200 and 1000 °C when the CMTs are 1300 or 1500 °C. For these CMTs the stiffness increase during cooling is not lost due to repeated thermal cycling, in contrast to cases where the CMT is 1100 °C and lower.

Figs. 20 through 25 show the damping, as quantified by the inverse quality factor, according to Eq. 2, as a function of temperature for the first, second and third heating and cooling cycles. Despite the large data scatter, which is typical for damping data of this type [24], it is immediately evident that the level (order of magnitude) of damping is similar in all cases, that the characteristic features are reproducible and that there are significant systematic differences in the temperature dependence of damping between heating and cooling (compared to which the differences between the individual cycles, albeit existent, are of secondary importance). Because of the latter, it makes sense to treat heating and cooling separately.

Concerning the heating branches, see Figs. 20 through 22, the following features are characteristic: the first heating branches in Fig. 20 exhibit small damping maxima at approximately 200, 350 and 860 °C, a broad and shallow valley (minimum) in the range 400–800 °C and a broad and high maximum centered around 1160–1170 °C. Note that in the temperature range 1100–1230 °C the damping is so high that the inverse quality factor (higher than 0.1) is actually not a valid measure of damping any more and has therefore not been calculated by the IET software. However, in contrast to similar cases when dissipative effects become too high (“diverge”), e.g. due to creep, in this case the possibility to calculate damping is not irretrievably lost, because at temperatures higher than 1230 °C the decreasing damping signal is again very sharp

Fig. 19. Cumulative hysteresis parameter as a function of temperature.

Fig. 20. Damping (inverse quality factor) as a function of temperature for the first heating branches of cycles with different CMTs (900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C).

Fig. 21. Damping (inverse quality factor) as a function of temperature for the second heating branches of cycles with different CMTs (900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C).

Fig. 22. Damping (inverse quality factor) as a function of temperature for the third heating branches of cycles with different CMTs (900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C).

and clear. For this reason it is possible to estimate the position of this high-temperature damping peak quite reliably to approximately 1160–1170 °C. During the second and third heating, Figs. 21 and 22, the low-temperature features are much more blurred and the feature at 860 °C appears at best as a shoulder, but the high-temperature damping peak

Fig. 23. Damping (inverse quality factor) as a function of temperature for the first cooling branches of cycles with different CMTs (900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C).

Fig. 24. Damping (inverse quality factor) as a function of temperature for the second cooling branches of cycles with different CMTs (900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C).

Fig. 25. Damping (inverse quality factor) as a function of temperature for the third cooling branches of cycles with different CMTs (900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C).

is again situated around 1160–1170 °C. The origin of this high-temperature damping peak is not completely clear but it is certainly related to the compositional and structural changes in the glass melt caused by the dissolution of the pseudowollastonite crystals and the

dendrites, see Fig. 2, possibly in combination with a transient crystallization of tridymite and / or cristobalite, followed by their re-dissolution at higher temperatures. Indeed, the low scatter and decreasing absolute values of damping at temperatures above 1230 °C is likely due to the formation of a homogeneous glass melt with relatively low viscosity.

The cooling branches, see Figs. 23 through 25, exhibit interesting and characteristic differences compared to the heating branches: while the damping maximum at 350 °C is retained at the same temperature as during heating, the lower-temperature maximum is shifted from 200 °C to approximately 180 °C and two new features appear in all cooling curves, namely a clear damping minimum at around 250 °C and a much less distinct, but still visible, minimum at around 100 °C. Much more important, however, is the fact that the high-temperature region of the cooling branches is not only significantly different from that of the heating branches but also exhibits significant changes with increasing number of cycles (which is not observed for the heating branches). In particular, during cooling from the CMT of 1500 °C, the high-temperature damping peak is broadened and shifted from 1160–1170 °C to much lower temperatures (900–1000 °C), while further temperature decrease reveals a relative sharp damping minimum at 520 ± 30 °C. By contrast, cooling from the CMT of 1300 °C reveals drastically different features, which are best visible in the third cycle, Fig. 25 (but are present in the first and second cycle as well): a distinct damping peak at around 1220 °C, followed by a featureless plateau down to approximately 900 °C, followed by a steep decrease towards a double well with damping minima at 660 and 530 °C, thus revealing a “fine structure” in the aforementioned broad and shallow damping valley between 400 and 800 °C. The fact that damping is generally low in this temperature range has to be attributed to the absence of phase transitions (and microstructural changes such as microcracking) in this temperature range but the interpretation of sharp damping minima is not obvious. Concerning damping maxima, it is well known that they always indicate dissipative processes [24]. Some of these maxima can be unambiguously attributed to phase transitions. For example, the damping maximum at 200 °C (during heating) and 180 °C (during cooling) is clearly related to the phase transition between low- and high-cristobalite. On the other hand, the damping maximum at around 350 °C, which seems to be in some way related to the change of slope of the temperature dependence of Young’s modulus, see Figs. 10–13, cannot be explained by any known phase transition and is probably related to microstructural changes, e.g. microcracking. The detailed interpretation of these features has to be left for future research.

4. Conclusions and outlook

1. The temperature dependences of Young’s modulus and damping of silica refractories during thermal cycling (heating and cooling with rates of 5 °C/min) between room temperature and cycle maximum temperatures (CMTs) of 900, 1100, 1300 and 1500 °C have been characterized via the impulse excitation technique (IET).
2. The phase composition and microstructure of silica refractories have been characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) before and after thermal cycling to 1500 °C. It has been shown that after cycling to 1500 °C the glass phase content has increased from ~2 % to ~10 %, because pseudowollastonite crystals and a dendritic phase are dissolved in the glass melt and have no time to recrystallize during cooling.
3. Mercury porosimetry of silica refractories before and after thermal cycling indicates a slight microcrack growth due to thermal cycling. However, the submicrometer pore size (representing the microcracks) is larger for CMTs of 900 and 1100 °C (~ 500 nm) than for CMTs of 1300 and 1500 °C (~ 415 nm), which indicates healing (microcrack closure) in the latter case. On the other hand, the supermicrometer pore size is smaller for CMTs of 900 and 1100 °C (16–17 μm) than for CMTs of 1300 and 1500 °C (~ 19 μm), which

- may be caused by the closure of small pores (making them inaccessible for mercury) in the latter case. Both effects can be caused by the glass melt at high temperature.
- The results of dilatometric measurements are closely related to those of IET measurements. In particular, the phase transitions of tridymite (at 112–115 °C and 143–150 °C) and cristobalite (at 231–241 °C during heating and 200 ± 2 °C during cooling) are clearly visible in dilatometry and have their clearly identifiable counterparts in the IET measurements. The results also show that the dilatometric behavior of silica refractories is not significantly affected by thermal cycling. Expansion coefficients are important input data for thermal shock parameter estimation.
 - It has been shown that silica refractories are unique materials with a very unusual thermomechanical memory. This memory enables tailoring the stiffness of the material via its thermal history. For example, for one and the same material (i.e. materials with the same phase composition, porosity and microstructure), Young's modulus at 800 °C (600 °C) can be tailored to be in the range from 19 ± 2 GPa (13 ± 2 GPa) to 31.5 ± 1.5 GPa (31 ± 2 GPa). The CMT has been shown to be the main control parameter. For a practical application of this remarkable finding the batch-to-batch and sample-to-sample variability of industrial products has to be taken into account.
 - Damage accumulation has been observed for heating-cooling cycles with CMTs of 900 and 1100 °C, but not for those with CMTs of 1300 and 1500 °C. On the contrary, the latter seem to indicate a slight increase of Young's modulus with each cycle, probably as a consequence of healing (microcrack closure) mediated by the glass melt at high temperature. This confirms previous findings on similar silica materials where repeated thermal cycling with a CMT of 1200 °C leads to almost identical and closed loops of the temperature dependence of Young's modulus during heating and cooling (i.e. exhibiting neither damage nor healing).
 - Hysteresis parameters have been introduced as a new concept to quantify the changes of stiffness between heating and cooling. Two variants of this parameter have been introduced, of which the first (incremental) quantifies the changes within one heating-cooling cycle and the second (cumulative) quantifies the changes due to repeated cycling. Negative values, i.e. higher Young's modulus during cooling compared to heating, are observed between 200 and 1000 °C when the CMTs are 1300 or 1500 °C. For these CMTs the stiffness increase during cooling is not lost due to repeated thermal cycling, in contrast to cases where the CMT is 900 °C and 1100 °C.
 - The temperature dependence of damping (i.e. anelastic behavior quantified via the so-called inverse quality factor) exhibits large data scatter but is well reproducible and shows several characteristic features. Some of these features can be clearly assigned to phase

transitions (e.g. the damping maximum around 200 °C is related to the cristobalite transition), while others are not easily interpretable (e.g. the damping minima and the damping maximum around 350 °C). The high-temperature damping maximum at 1160–1170 °C during heating might be related to a transient crystallization of cristobalite and / or tridymite which are re-dissolved in the glass phase at higher temperatures.

Future work aiming at assessing the suitability of silica refractories for high-temperature thermal energy storage (TES) applications should focus on thermal cycling not only between room temperature and elevated temperatures but also between two different elevated temperatures. Moreover, the influence of the dwell time on elastic properties should be investigated.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Eva Gregorová: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Miroslav Kotouček:** Resources. **Petra Šimonová:** Investigation, Data curation. **Willi Pabst:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Vojtěch Nečina:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Petr Bezdička:** Validation, Investigation. **Lucie Kotrbová:** Investigation. **Gert Schmidt:** Investigation. **Jana Hubálková:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ivona Sedlářová:** Investigation. **Christos G. Aneziris:** Validation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability statement

The original raw data for this paper are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13286184>.

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Appendix A. True expansion coefficients

Figures A1 through A3 show the true expansion coefficients (ECs), more precisely linear thermal expansion coefficients, for two heating-cooling cycles (first from room temperature to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C, second from 160 °C to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C) for as-supplied (i.e. previously uncycled) silica refractory samples as well as for samples that have undergone three complete heating-cooling cycles from room temperature to cycle maximum temperatures (CMTs) of 900 °C and 1500 °C, respectively, and back to 160 °C. The temperatures of the EC maxima are listed in Table 5 in the main text and correspond to the phase transitions from low- to middle-tridymite (112–115 °C), middle- to high-tridymite (143–150 °C) and low- to high-cristobalite (231–241 °C during heating and 200 ± 2 °C during cooling).

Figure A1. Temperature dependence of the true expansion coefficient (true EC) for two heating-cooling cycles (first from room temperature to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C, second from 160 °C to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C) for uncycled silica refractory samples.

Figure A2. Temperature dependence of the true expansion coefficient (true EC) for two heating-cooling cycles (first from room temperature to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C, second from 160 °C to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C) for silica refractory samples three times cycled with a CMT of 900 °C.

Figure A3. Temperature dependence of the true expansion coefficient (true EC) for two heating-cooling cycles (first from room temperature to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C, second from 160 °C to 1450 °C and back to 160 °C) for silica refractory samples three times cycled with a CMT of 1500 °C.

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